

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF EFFECT OF REPEATED MICROWAVE DISINFECTION ON THE SURFACE HARDNESS OF POLYETHERETHERKETONE (PEEK): AN IN-VITRO STUDY

1. Dr. Twinkle Lokhande
Assistant Professor
Address: Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research center
Digdoh hills, Hingana Road, Nagpur, 440019
2. Dr. Neelam Pande
Head of Department and Professor
Address: Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research center
Digdoh hills, Hingana Road, Nagpur, 440019
3. Dr. Akhil Rathi (*)
Associate Professor
Address: Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research center
Digdoh hills, Hingana Road, Nagpur, 440019
4. Dr. Saeesh Deshpande
Professor
Address: Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research center
Digdoh hills, Hingana Road, Nagpur, 440019
5. Dr. Anuj Chandak
Reader
Address: Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research center
Digdoh hills, Hingana Road, Nagpur, 440019

ABSTRACT

AIM: -

To evaluate and compare the effect of repeated microwave disinfection on surface hardness of polyetheretherketone (PEEK).

METHODOLOGY:

Total 60 samples of PEEK were milled and fabricated by using CAD/CAM milling unit. These were divided into 4 groups of 15 samples in each. The included groups were Group SH-0 MWC (microwave disinfection control), Group SH-1 MWC, Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC. Microwave oven set at 650 Watt for 3 minutes was considered as 1 cycle of microwave disinfection. This one cycle repeated for 3 times and 5 times for Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC respectively. After disinfection, each group was tested for surface micro hardness test, on universal testing machine.

RESULT:

The results of the study reveal that there is a significant difference in surface hardness between the groups. The highest surface hardness was present with Group SH-5 MWC followed by Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-1 MWC

CONCLUSION:

PEEK material can be disinfected safely by using microwave repeatedly for disinfecting the dentures up to 650 W for 3 min. Repeated microwave disinfection can increase the surface hardness of PEEK material. This material can be disinfected by either of the microwave disinfection cycle viz. 1 cycle of microwave disinfection or with 3 cycles of microwave disinfection or with 5 cycles of microwave disinfection. This may not make much difference during regular use of PEEK in clinical conditions.

KEYWORDS: *Disinfection, denture, microwave, PEEK.*

INTRODUCTION

Prosthodontics is a speciality that deals with the replacement of missing teeth along with associated soft tissues and hard structures. The use of resins as denture base materials was initiated by Dr. Leo Bakeland in 1909, because of its outstanding esthetics, easy processing, relining, and repair techniques.

Biocompatibility is a very essential requirement in all restorative materials, followed by physical and mechanical properties which guarantee proper structural and functional durability over extensive period of time. Hence now a days Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) has been introduced in dentistry for many purpose as it gives advance effect in dental materials.[1-3] PEEK is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic biomaterial. PEEK has many clinical advantages like less hypersensitivity and allergic reactions. [4,5]

With recurrent exposure towards the microorganisms containing salivary fluid and blood, the dental profession has become on a higher risk for certain infectious disorders or diseases as compared to the general population[6-11]. The routine care provided to the patients puts the dentist at higher risk of acquiring diseases due to chances of cross-infection.[12]

Another concern which needs to be considered is the effect of these disinfectants on the denture material. Literature reports alteration of mechanical and physical properties of materials by subjecting them to disinfectants. Moreover, certain chemicals possessed cytotoxicity risk and thus were considered inappropriate for patients as well at chair side for the dentist for disinfection.[13]

Apart from these traditionally used methods, other alternative methods are microwave irradiation and photodynamic therapy.[14,15] The photodynamic therapy involves the use of photosensitizer which is a photo active dye activated by a specific wavelength light in the presence of oxygen, which further results in highly toxic free radical that possess cell structures leading to inactivation of pathogens. In case of microwave irradiation, electromagnetic waves of frequency close to television and aircraft radar are used to irradiate the microorganisms from the denture materials. The clinical relevance microwave disinfection is that this procedure can be performed quickly and repeatedly, without the use of toxic, pungent, or allergenic chemicals. It is demonstrated that short period of microwave energy inhibits the growth of pathogenic microorganism. Hence microwave irradiation can be used as a disinfection method in dentistry.[16]

The disinfection procedures cause changes in hardness of the material. Hardness is defined as “Resistance to indentation”. The surface hardness of a denture is based upon its ability to resist indentation or scratching.[17] Measurement of surface hardness of any material indicate up to what range the masticatory forces can be resisted[18]. PEEK is introduced in dentistry as a dimensionally stable thermoplastic material [19]. Since microwave (MW) disinfection of PEEK material is not yet studied, this study aims to evaluate the effect of repeated cycle of microwave disinfection on the surface hardness of Polyetheretherketone material.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

The material and method are subdivided into following groups:

A. Materials and Armamentarium (Table. 1)

Sr no.	Materials / Instruments	Manufacturer	Batch number
1.	PEEK material used for fabrication	Bredent breCAM. BioHPP	497897
2.	CAD/CAM Milling unit	Sirona Dental Systems GmbH Fabrikstr. 31	6384700
3.	Microwave Disinfectant Unit	Samsung smart oven	SM397623B00
4.	Universal Testing Machine	Reichert Austria	363798
5.	Micro motor and Lab handpiece	Marathon	3A556B
6.	4 Beakers and 4 bottles for storage of samples	-----	-----

METHODOLOGY:

Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) blank of 98 mm. x 10 mm. was used to fabricate the test samples. The size of the samples was decided on the basis of requirement of surface micro hardness test, as per ADA specifications. All samples were tested by using the Micro-Hardness Tester (Company Reichert, Austria SR. No. 363798).

The steps involved in the fabrication of the test samples are as follows:

STL (Standard Tessellation Language) file:-

STL is a file format native to the stereolithographic CAD software created by 3D system. It is widely used for rapid prototyping, 3D printing and computer aided manufacturing. According to ADA specification no. 12, for micro hardness test, a disc block measuring 15 mm. in diameter and 5 mm. in thickness was used for preparing all the samples. This required sample size with its diagrammatic representation was sent to the software professionals. Accordingly, the final STL file was designed and sent to the laboratory for milling from the plank of PEEK. (Fig.1 and 2).

Fabrication of samples:-

Plank of PEEK material having dimensions of 98 mm. diameter and 10 mm. in thickness was used for the fabrication of samples. In the milling machine system, fabrication of near about 15 samples was possible from one plank of PEEK material, accordingly these were adjusted in the software machine. PEEK plank was placed in the milling machine had started for milling to fabricate the samples. The milling machine has total 3 different textured burs, which was automatically used one after the other. During this procedure, there was formation of heat. So, the inlet with coolant spray gets activated at one end, at the same time discarded water was removed from the attached outlet, at another end. The milled samples were not separated completely by the machine; rather all were attached at their corners in very thin portions (Fig.3). Finally, their attached ends were cut carefully using laboratory hand piece. In this way, total 60 samples were fabricated in the CAD CAM milling machine. They were divided into 4 groups for various cycles of microwave disinfection testing. All the

samples were stored in distilled water in beaker at room temperature, till the surface hardness tests were performed (Fig. 4).

There were total 60 samples divided into 4 groups of 15 samples each for surface hardness (SH) test.

1 MWC:- 1 cycle of microwave disinfection was referred at 650 watt for 3 minutes.

In this way, the Group 0, 1, 3 and 5 cycles of microwave disinfection were considered for the surface hardness testing.

1. Group SH-0 MWC:- Samples without undergoing microwave disinfection (Control).
2. Group SH-1 MWC:- Samples with 1 cycle of microwave disinfection.
3. Group SH-3 MWC:- Samples with 3 cycles of microwave disinfection.
4. Group SH-5 MWC:- Samples with 5 cycles of microwave disinfection.

1. Microwave disinfection of the samples:-

Initially, the samples of control group were stored in plastic beaker containing distilled water for easy identification. For microwave disinfection cycles, samples were stored in glass beaker. The microwave oven, was set at 650 wattage (W) for 3 min referred as “one disinfection cycle of microwave irradiation.”⁽⁴⁹⁾ Experimental group samples were disinfected one after the other, according to the number of cycle of microwave disinfection. Thus, for 1MWC, microwave oven was set at 650 W for 3 minutes. This 1 cycle was repeated 3 times for 3 MWC and 5 times for 5 MWC without any break. After completion of MWCs, all the samples were again stored in the distilled water, till the micro-hardness tests were performed.

2. Surface Micro hardness test of the samples:-

All the samples were initially conditioned in incubator, immersed in distilled water at 37°C for 48 h, to simulate oral environment, before they were tested on Universal testing machine. Later, the samples were transferred into the bottle containing distilled water where each group of testing was labelled (Fig.5).

The samples were tested using the Vickers hardness (HV) test method. For evaluation of surface hardness, the universal Micro Hardness Tester machine (Reichert Austria Make, Sr.No.363798, Load applied- 50 g, Reference Standard: ISO 6507) was used(Fig.18). This machine consists of indenting the test material with a diamond indenter, (Fig.19) in the form of a right pyramid with a square base and an angle of 136° between opposite faces subjected to a load of 0.05 kgf (50gmf). The load was applied for 10 - 15 seconds. After removal of the load, two diagonals of the indentation, left on the surface of each sample, was measured using a microscope and their average value was calculated. The area of the sloping surface of indentation was calculated. Average value of two diagonals was considered as a final value of diagonal. The hardness value (HV) quotient was obtained by dividing the kgf load by the square millimeter area of indentation.

The HV number was calculated in (HV) using the formula:

$$HV = (1.854 \times F) / d^2$$

Where, F = Load (kgf),

d = Arithmetic mean of the two diagonals, d1 and d2 mm.

Two readings were obtained for determining the hardness and finally the average value of these two readings was consider as a hardness value for particular sample of their respective group.

RESULTS

The present study was conducted to evaluate the difference in surface hardness of PEEK material without microwave disinfection with that of PEEK material undergoing 1 microwave cycle, 3 microwave cycles and 5 microwave cycles for disinfection.

One-way ANOVA was applied to assess the difference between the groups followed by post hoc test.

Table 2:- This represents the mean surface hardness in groups Group SH-0 MWC, Group SH-1 MWC, Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC Group. In Group SH-0 Control, the mean surface hardness was 15.88 N/mm.² with standard deviation of 1.33. The minimum and maximum surface hardness was 14.7 N/mm.² and 18.9 N/mm.². In Group SH-1 MWC, the mean surface hardness was 17.02 N/mm.² with standard deviation of 1.04. The minimum and maximum surface hardness was 15.41 N/mm.² and 18.80 N/mm.². In Group SH-3 MWC, the mean surface hardness was 23.30 N/mm.² with standard deviation of 1.13. The minimum and maximum surface hardness was 21.69 N/mm.² and 25.35 N/mm.². In Group SH-5 MWC, the mean surface hardness was 24.48 N/mm.² with standard deviation of 1.81. The minimum and maximum surface hardness was 22.88 N/mm.² and 27.96 N/mm.².

Graph1:- Represents the bar diagram with surface hardness in all the four groups. The x-axis represents the groups i.e., Group SH-0 Control, Group SH-1 MWC, Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC and the y-axis represents the mean surface hardness.

Table 3:- It represents difference in mean surface hardness between Group SH-0 Control, Group SH-1 MWC, Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC. After applying One-way ANOVA test the F value was 153.392. There was a significant difference in the surface hardness between the groups with $p < 0.0001$.

A statistical significant difference is present in the hardness between Group SH-0, Group SH-1 MWC, Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC.

Table 4:- It determines exactly which groups are presenting with the difference in mean surface roughness, post hoc Tukey test was applied. The table represents the groups showing significant difference in mean surface hardness. A significant difference in mean surface hardness was present between: Group SH-0 and Group SH-3 with mean difference of 7.41 and $p < 0.0001$, Group SH-0 and Group SH-5 MWC with mean difference of 8.59 and $p < 0.0001$, Group SH-1 MWC and Group SH-3 with mean difference of 6.28 and $p < 0.0001$, Group SH-1 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC with mean difference of 7.45 and $p < 0.0001$.

A statistical significant difference is present between –

Group SH-0 MWC Control Group and Group SH-3 MWC

Group SH-0 Control Group and Group SH-5 MWC

Group SH-1 MWC and Group SH-3 MWC

Group SH-1 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC

Hardness: Group SH-5 MWC > Group SH-3 MWC > Group SH-1 MWC > Group SH-0 MWC Control Group

No statistical significant difference in surface hardness was present between: Group SH-0 Control Group and Group SH-1 MWC, Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC with $p > 0.05$.

Overall, the results of the study reveal that there is a significant difference in surface hardness between the groups. The highest surface hardness was present with Group SH-5 MWC followed by Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-1 MWC. The Group SH-0 MWC Control Group showed the least surface hardness. The results indicate that the microwave disinfecting cycles affect the surface hardness of PEEK material. With increase in number of cycles, the surface hardness of PEEK material increases.

TABLES AND GRAPH

Table 2:- Mean hardness in control and the intervention groups

Groups	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Group SH-0 MWC Control	15	14.7	18.9	15.88	1.33
Group SH-1 MWC	15	15.41	18.8	17.02	1.04
Group SH-3 MWC	15	21.69	25.35	23.30	1.13
Group SH-5 MWC	15	22.88	27.96	24.48	1.81

Table 3:- Difference in the hardness between the groups

Groups	Mean	F	Significance (p)
Group SH-0 MWC Control Group	15.88	153.392	< 0.0001*

Group SH-1 MWC	17.02		
Group SH-3 MWC	23.30		
Group SH-5 MWC	24.48		

*Significance at $p < 0.05$

Table 4:- Post hoc Tukey test

Groups		Mean Difference	Significance (p)
Group SH-0 MWC Control Group	Group SH-1 MWC	1.13400	.114
	Group SH-3 MWC	7.41933	<.0001*
	Group SH-5 MWC	8.59200	<.0001*
Group SH-1 MWC	Group SH-0 MWC	1.13400	.114
	Group SH-3 MWC	6.28533	<.0001*
	Group SH-5 MWC	7.45800	<.0001*
Group SH-3 MWC	Group SH-0 MWC	7.41933	<.0001*
	Group SH-1 MWC	6.28533	<.0001*
	Group SH-5 MWC	1.17267	.096
Group SH-5 MWC	Group SH-0 MWC	8.59200	<.0001*
	Group SH-1 MWC	7.45800	<.0001*
	Group SH-3 MWC	1.17267	.096

*Significance at $p < 0.05$

GRAPH

Graph 1- Bar diagram representing mean hardness in control and intervention groups

DISCUSSION

Denture plaque is a structured community of microorganisms that is surrounded by self-produced polymeric matrix. The effects of microorganisms not just stay confined to the patients but become a potential source of contamination from patient to the dentist as well as laboratory person. In a study reported by **Powell et al**, [20] 67% of the dental material sent from the clinic was found to be contaminated with opportunistic pathogens. Thus, keeping the dentures clean eradicated disease spread to patients, dentist and laboratory technician.

Apart from these, immersion of dentures in 2% alkaline glutaraldehyde, 3% aqueous formaldehyde, 1% sodium hypochlorite, 3.78% sodium perborate, 4% chlorhexidine proved to be effective in reducing microorganism contamination over the denture surfaces. Though these methods disinfect the dentures but they also alter the physical and mechanical properties of denture materials. The studies have reported the detrimental effect of these solutions on surface roughness, hardness and transverse strength. Moreover, the color stability also gets significantly affected resulting in poor esthetics [21].

With the focus on a method that will disinfect the denture material and prevent contamination and at the same time retain its mechanical and physical properties, microwaving the dentures have emerged as an effective method. The study conducted by **Rohrer SC and Bulard SC in 1985** [22] reported that the dentures contaminated with fungi and aerobic bacteria were sterilized in 10 minutes by microwaving at an irradiation of 720W. Similarly, **Webb BC [23] et al in 1988** demonstrated 6 minutes of microwaving at 350W to be more effective in inactivating the microorganisms than soaking the denture in the disinfecting solution. **Buergers et al 2008** [24] also mentioned in their study a significant decrease in *Candida albicans* from the denture surface after irradiating for 6 minutes with 800W. In addition to this, irradiation with 650W for 6 minutes provided denture

surface free from colonization of staphylococcus aureus, Candida albicans, bacillus subtilis and pseudomonas aeruginosa.

The present study provided the effect of repeated microwave disinfection on the surface hardness of Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) material, when subjected to 1, 3 and 5 microwave disinfection cycles. A study by **Godara A et al (2007)**⁽²²⁾ where the effect of gamma radiation or steam sterilization on thermoplastic matrix composite polyetheretherketone (PEEK), reinforced with carbon fibers was evaluated. The presence of fibers can also impose restrictions on the normal plastic-flow deformation mechanism of the matrix, hence inducing an increase in the hardness values within the proximity of the fiber surface. Whereas study done by **Bodden L et al (2017)** though not related to microwave disinfection, but the effect of heating / quenching process on the PEEK material demonstrated that the Martens hardness of PEEK material significantly decreased [25]. It was suspected that the crystalline structure of PEEK melted and the matrix stayed in amorphous state through quenching. An increase of the indentation modulus affects the stiffness of the material, making it less flexible and more translucent.

One more study done on PMMA by **Arima et al in 1996**, showed that the changes in surface hardness of the material is greatly influence by the chemical composition. As with the addition of cross-linking agents, the solubility of the material decreases[26]. Similarly, **Machado AL et al (2009)**, evaluated the effect of microwave disinfection on Vicker hardness of the material was determined on different types of PMMA. They found increase in the mean hardness of the reline resin materials while the hardness of heat polymerised resin remained unchanged [27]. They explained this change in hardness was due the amount of unreacted monomer in the specimens was reduced during the disinfection procedures.

In addition, microwave irradiation causes rearrangement of the polymer chains and the extent of distortion of the material by the nature of polymerization process. This traps the stresses within the poly-matrix which are then released during microwave disinfection, resulting an increase in surface hardness. In these study the surface hardness of PEEK material increased after microwave disinfection.[28-31]

Prechtel et al 2019 in their study mentioned that the method of fabrication can also affect the surface hardness of PEEK materials. The PEEK restorations can be fabricated by CAD/CAM milling, which is a subtractive method or by 3D printing which is an additive method. CAD/CAM Milled specimens showed higher hardness than 3D printed [32]. This fact was explained by the standardized conditions of manufacturing by CAD/CAM milling, where a controlled crystallization process of the thermoplastic material take place. Whereas in 3D printed samples, the filament was melted in the extruder and subjected to a more or less controlled crystallization, after the printing process, which was influenced by factors like temperature management and cooling procedure.

In the present study also all the samples were made by CAD-CAM milling process, by standardised software procedures. There was least mean difference between Group SH-0 MWC and Group SH-1 MWC, when compared to other groups (Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC). This was due to temperature change during microwave disinfection process, where the diffusion coefficient was increased, while the equilibrium absorption remained same. Thus, as the microwave disinfection cycle increased, there may lead to change in hardness, due to moisture absorption in polymer through diffusion and capillary process which induce plastic

deformation. As the higher level of water gets absorbed, the process facilitated the plasticizing effect on the material surface, leading to moderately lesser surface hardness as compared to remaining two groups (Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC).

In Group SH-3 MWC and Group SH-5 MWC, with increased microwave cycles, there was further increase in temperature. Moreover, the vibrations caused by microwave irradiation lead to vibration of the water molecules within the water bath, thereby resulting in friction. At the same time, with faster moisture diffusion the material likely showed faster rate of hardening[33-36]. Another reason might be due to further increase in the temperature, which may lead to heating induced deformation in crystallinity and microscopic structures, resulting in increased hardness of the PEEK samples in these groups[37-43].

According to kliromonos et al, microwave disinfection could be a safe safe alternative for the disinfection of denture bases and liners compared to the chemical one, when the procedure is carried out in dry conditions, but could possibly cause dimensional changes of clinical significance on them when the irradiation takes place in wet environment [44]. The present study also showed the important role of microwave disinfection for PEEK material as compare to chemical sterilization.

Clinical Implications:-

The microwave disinfection is less time taking and easy procedure for disinfection of dental prosthesis. The newer PEEK material successfully used in the day to day clinical practice, can also be disinfected repeatedly by using either of the cycle of microwave disinfection. Even though the hardness of PEEK increased with the increased number of microwave disinfection cycles, it is an appropriate material to fabricate the prosthesis, to withstand or resist the heavy masticatory forces.

Limitations of the study:-

There were some limitations in this study, being an in-vitro study it could not replicate all the conditions present in the oral environment. The hardness value was checked in the laboratory by applying straight perpendicular load. However, intraorally masticatory forces are different and are multi directional.

Scope for further studies:-

1. Other parameters for mechanical properties and color stability can be evaluated after microwave disinfection.
2. Samples fabricated by additive method i.e. 3D printing can also be evaluated.

CONCLUSION:-

Within the limitation of the study, following conclusion can be drawn:

1. PEEK material can be disinfected safely by using microwave.
2. The microwave disinfection method can be used repeatedly for disinfecting the dentures up to 650 W for 3 min.
3. Repeated microwave disinfection can increase the surface hardness of PEEK material.

This material can be disinfested by either of the microwave disinfection cycle viz. 1 cycle of microwave disinfection or with 3 cycles of microwave disinfection or with 5 cycles of microwave disinfection. This may not make much difference during regular use of PEEK in clinical conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

NIL

REFERENCES:

1. Zhao J, Wang X. Chapter 3 - Dental Prostheses. In: Shen JZ, Kosmač T, editors. *Advanced Ceramics for Dentistry* [Internet]. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann; 2014 [cited 2022 Mar 9]. p. 23–49.
2. Shrivastava SP, Dable R, Raj APN, Mutneja P, Srivastava SB, Haque M. Comparison of Mechanical Properties of PEEK and PMMA: An In Vitro Study. *J Contemp Dent Pract*. 2021 Feb 1;22(2):179–83.
3. Najeeb S, Zafar MS, Khurshid Z, Siddiqui F. Applications of polyetheretherketone (PEEK) in oral implantology and prosthodontics. *J Prosthodont Res*. 2016 Jan;60(1):12–9.
4. Kurtz SM. Chapter 6 - Chemical and Radiation Stability of PEEK. In: Kurtz SM, editor. *PEEK Biomaterials Handbook* [Internet]. Oxford: William Andrew Publishing; 2012 [cited 2022 Mar 9]. p. 75–9.
5. Barkarmo S, Wennerberg A, Hoffman M, Kjellin P, Breiding K, Handa P, et al. Nano-hydroxyapatite-coated PEEK implants: A pilot study in rabbit bone. *J Biomed Mater Res A*. 2013;101A(2):465–71.
6. Ayatollahi J, Ayatollahi F, Ardekani AM, Bahrololoomi R, Ayatollahi J, Ayatollahi A, et al. Occupational hazards to dental staff. *Dent Res J*. 2012;9(1):2–7.
7. Upendran A, Gupta R, Geiger Z. Dental Infection Control. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 [cited 2022 Mar 9].
8. Jain S, Yadav B, Phogat S, Madan R. DISINFECTION IN PROSTHODONTICS. *Int J Dent Health Sci*. 2014 Jan 1;1:779–87.
9. McCarthy GM. Risk of transmission of viruses in the dental office. *J Can Dent Assoc*. 2000 Nov;66(10):554–5, 557.

10. Cleveland JL, Gray SK, Harte JA, Robison VA, Moorman AC, Gooch BF. Transmission of blood-borne pathogens in US dental health care settings: 2016 update. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1939. 2016 Sep;147(9):729–38.
11. Abbas AKM, Al-Kebsi AM, Madar EM, Al-Shamahy HA. Hepatitis B Virus among Dental Clinic Workers and the Risk Factors Contributing for its Infection. *Online J Dent Oral Health*. 2018 Oct 17;1(2):1–6.
12. Chemical Disinfectants | Disinfection & Sterilization Guidelines | Guidelines Library | Infection Control | CDC [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2022 Mar 9].
13. Klironomos T, Katsimpali A, Polyzois G. The Effect of Microwave Disinfection on Denture Base Polymers, Liners and Teeth: A Basic Overview. *Acta Stomatol Croat*. 2015 Sep;49(3):242–53.
14. Vlahova AP, Kissev CK, Popova EV, Todorov GR. Photodynamic Disinfection of Dentures. *Am J Infect Dis Microbiol*. 2013 Jan 23;1(2):34–7.
15. Pavan S, Arioli Filho JN, Santos PH dos, Mollo Jr. F de A. Effect of microwave treatments on dimensional accuracy of maxillary acrylic resin denture base. *Braz Dent J*. 2005 Aug;16(2):119–23.
16. Vergani C, Ribeiro D, Dovigo L, Sanita PV, Pavarina A. Microwave assisted disinfection method in dentistry. In 2011.
17. PhD KJA DMD, Shen C, Rawls HR. *Phillips' Science of Dental Materials*. Elsevier Health Sciences; 2012. 588 p.
18. Muhsin SA, Hatton PV, Johnson A, Sereno N, Wood DJ. Determination of Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) mechanical properties as a denture material. *Saudi Dent J*. 2019 Jul;31(3):382–91.
19. Azzarri MJ, Cortizo MS, Alessandrini JL. Effect of the curing conditions on the properties of an acrylic denture base resin microwave-polymerised. *J Dent*. 2003 Sep;31(7):463–8.
20. Powell GL, Runnells RD, Saxon BA, Whisenant BK. The presence and identification of organisms transmitted to dental laboratories. *J Prosthet Dent*. 1990 Aug;64(2):235–7.

21. Lai C-P, Tsai M-H, Chen M, Chang H-S, Tay H-H. Morphology and properties of denture acrylic resins cured by microwave energy and conventional water bath. *Dent Mater Off Publ Acad Dent Mater*. 2004 Feb;20(2):133–41.
22. Rohrer MD, Bulard RA. Microwave sterilization. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1939. 1985 Feb;110(2):194–8. Godara A, Raabe D, Green S. The influence of sterilization processes on the micromechanical properties of carbon fiber-reinforced PEEK composites for bone implant applications. *Acta Biomater*. 2007 Mar;3(2):209–20.
23. Webb BC, Thomas CJ, Harty DW, Willcox MD. Effectiveness of two methods of denture sterilization. *J Oral Rehabil*. 1998 Jun;25(6):416–23.
24. Buegers R, Rosentritt M, Schneider-Brachert W, Behr M, Handel G, Hahnel S. Efficacy of denture disinfection methods in controlling *Candida albicans* colonization in vitro. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2008 Jun;66(3):174–80.
25. Bodden L, Lümke N, Köhler V, Eichberger M, Stawarczyk B. Impact of the heating/quenching process on the mechanical, optical and thermodynamic properties of polyetheretherketone (PEEK) films. *Dent Mater Off Publ Acad Dent Mater*. 2017 Dec;33(12):1436–44.
26. Arima T, Murata H, Hamada T. The effects of cross-linking agents on the water sorption and solubility characteristics of denture base resin. *J Oral Rehabil*. 1996 Jul;23(7):476–80.
27. Machado AL, Breeding LC, Vergani CE, da Cruz Perez LE. Hardness and surface roughness of relines and denture base acrylic resins after repeated disinfection procedures. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2009 Aug;102(2):115–22.
28. Senna PM, Da Silva WJ, Faot F, Del Bel Cury AA. Microwave disinfection: cumulative effect of different power levels on physical properties of denture base resins. *J Prosthodont Off J Am Coll Prosthodont*. 2011 Dec;20(8):606–12.
29. Campanha NH, Pavarina AC, Jorge JH, Vergani CE, Machado AL, Giampaolo ET. The effect of long-term disinfection procedures on hardness property of resin denture teeth. *Gerodontology*. 2012 Jun;29(2):e571-576.

30. Vasconcelos LR, Consani RLX, Mesquita MF, Sinhoreti MAC. Effect of chemical and microwave disinfection on the surface microhardness of acrylic resin denture teeth. *J Prosthodont Off J Am Coll Prosthodont*. 2013 Jun;22(4):298–303.
31. Prechtel A, Reymus M, Edelhoff D, Hickel R, Stawarczyk B. Comparison of various 3D printed and milled PAEK materials: Effect of printing direction and artificial aging on Martens parameters. *Dent Mater Off Publ Acad Dent Mater*. 2020 Feb;36(2):197–209.
32. Ji S, Sun C, Zhao J, Liang F. Comparison and Analysis on Mechanical Property and Machinability about Polyetheretherketone and Carbon-Fibers Reinforced Polyetheretherketone. *Mater Basel Switz*. 2015 Jul 7;8(7):4118–30.
33. Stawarczyk B, Eichberger M, Uhrenbacher J, Wimmer T, Edelhoff D, Schmidlin PR. Three-unit reinforced polyetheretherketone composite FDPs: influence of fabrication method on load-bearing capacity and failure types. *Dent Mater J*. 2015;34(1):7–12.
34. Liebermann A, Wimmer T, Schmidlin PR, Scherer H, Löffler P, Roos M, et al. Physicomechanical characterization of polyetheretherketone and current esthetic dental CAD/CAM polymers after aging in different storage media. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2016 Mar;115(3):321-328.e2.
35. Heimer S, Schmidlin PR, Stawarczyk B. Discoloration of PMMA, composite, and PEEK. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2017 May;21(4):1191–200.
36. Awaja F, Cools P, Lohberger B, Nikiforov AY, Speranza G, Morent R. Functionalized, biocompatible, and impermeable nanoscale coatings for PEEK. *Mater Sci Eng C*. 2017 Jul 1;76:865–70.
37. Lümke N, Eichberger M, Stawarczyk B. Different PEEK qualities irradiated with light of different wavelengths: Impact on Martens hardness. *Dent Mater Off Publ Acad Dent Mater*. 2017 Sep;33(9):968–75.
38. Ma R, Guo D. Evaluating the bioactivity of a hydroxyapatite-incorporated polyetheretherketone biocomposite. *J Orthop Surg*. 2019 Jan 25;14(1):32.
39. Kumar A, Yap WT, Foo SL, Lee TK. Effects of Sterilization Cycles on PEEK for Medical Device Application. *Bioeng Basel Switz*. 2018 Feb 21;5(1):E18.

40. Alsadon O, Wood D, Patrick D, Pollington S. Comparing the optical and mechanical properties of PEKK polymer when CAD/CAM milled and pressed using a ceramic pressing furnace. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater.* 2019 Jan;89:234–6.
41. Niem T, Youssef N, Wöstmann B. Energy dissipation capacities of CAD-CAM restorative materials: A comparative evaluation of resilience and toughness. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2019 Jan;121(1):101–9.
42. Bathala L, Majeti V, Rachuri N, Singh N, Gedela S. The Role of Polyether Ether Ketone (Peek) in Dentistry – A Review. *J Med Life.* 2019;12(1):5–9.
43. Klur T, Hasan I, Ottersbach K, Stark H, Fichte M, Dirk C, et al. PEKK-made indirect temporary crowns and bridges: a clinical pilot study. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2019 Feb;23(2):771–7.
44. Klironomos T, Katsimpali A, Polyzois G. The Effect of Microwave Disinfection on Denture Base. *Polymers, Liners and Teeth: A Basic Overview. Acta Stomatol Croat.* 2015 Sep;49(3):242-53.

Fig. 1:- Plank/disc of PEEK material

Fig. 2:- Diagrammatic representation of sample and STL file of dimension 15 mm. X 5 mm.

Fig. 3:- Plank of PEEK placed in machine for milling by using bur and water spray for coolant.

Fig. 4:- Four groups suggest without microwave disinfection, 1 cycle of microwave disinfection, 3 cycle of microwave disinfection, 5 cycle of microwave disinfection.

Fig.5:- Samples kept in bottle filled with distilled in which white color denotes without microwave disinfection and coloured box labelled for number of microwave

Fig.6:- Sample kept in hardness testing machine